

Social media & web report

This social media and web report summarizes visually data extracted from the IPERION HS website and social media over the last year (October 2020 - September 2021).

The report highlights strenght and weakness in the IPERION HS communication strategy and offers useful insight to identify the audience, monitor engagement and schedule targeted contents.

Google Analytics

report

- Italy
- Spain
- US
- UK
- France
- Netherlands
- Germany
- China
- Finland
- Greece

Countries

Demographics

Users

13k

Sessions

22.6k

Page views

67.4k

Average session
duration

00:02:44

Visitors: New vs Returning

20%

Returning visitors

390

users registered

USER EXPERIENCE: customization

users

sessions

page views

Average duration session

00:02:44

	Page	Page Views	% Page Views
1.	/	11,961	17.74%
2.	/my-account/	3,203	4.75%
3.	/catalogue-of-services/	2,529	3.75%
4.	/dashboard/	2,301	3.41%
5.	/bot-traffic.xyz	2,018	2.99%
6.	/fixlab/	1,770	2.63%
7.	/cart/	1,711	2.54%
8.	/iperion-hsaccess/	1,643	2.44%
9.	/molab/	1,611	2.39%
10.	/catalogue/	1,435	2.13%

Behaviour

Bounce Rate

The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. The bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds

Channels

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

89,8%

Social media (mostly Facebook) drive users towards the events of IPERION HS (webinars, doctoral summer schools, calls, etc...)

IPERION HS

report

Countries

Demographics

Followers

1.144

Posts

127

Shares

659

Page
engagement

8.5k

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

16,6%

New followers

Sentiment

IPERION HS engages at any hour

Top post: key words

Iperion HS
17 June · 🌐

The 4th #HSAcademy webinar on scientific archives (ARCHLAB) will take place on July 6, 2021 at 3 pm CEST. Astrid Harth from @ugent will tell her experience with scientific archives working on the Ghent Altarpiece, while María Martín Gil from Instituto Nacional de Patrimonio Cultural will present the Iperion HS scientific archives and talk about how to access them.
Register here: <https://bit.ly/35ikUfz>
#webinar #heritagescience

Webinar #04 / July, 6th 2021

ARCHLAB & GHENT ALTARPIECE

**ASTRID HARTH &
MARÍA MARTIN GIL**

HSAcademy

✔ **Get more likes, comments and shares**
When you boost this post, you'll show it to more people.

6,586
People reached

201
Engagements

Boost post

👤 Michelle Picón Albarracín, Judit Zöldföldi and 4 others 1 Comment 24 shares

👍 Like 💬 Comment ➦ Share 🌐

Performance for your post

6,586 People Reached

82 Reactions, comments & shares ⓘ

54 👍 Like	7 On post	47 On shares
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1 ❤️ Love	0 On post	1 On shares
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3 Comments	1 On Post	2 On Shares
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24 Shares	24 On Post	0 On Shares
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119 Post Clicks

8 Photo views	37 Link clicks ⓘ	74 Other Clicks ⓘ
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NEGATIVE FEEDBACK

0 Hide post	0 Hide all posts
0 Report as spam	0 Unlike Page

Reported stats may be delayed from what appears on posts

Top post

A decorative graphic in the top right corner consisting of two yellow arcs above a blue geometric shape that resembles a stylized tower or a network node.

44%

Amplification Rate percentage

"It is the rate at which your followers take your content and share it through their networks" (Avinash Kaushik, Google)

IPERION HS

report

A dark blue network diagram consisting of four circular nodes connected by lines. The nodes are arranged in a zig-zag pattern: the first node is at the bottom left, the second is at the top center, the third is at the bottom center, and the fourth is at the top right. The word "report" is positioned above the nodes, with the 'o' in "report" aligned with the top-center node.

Followers

782

Posts

127

Shares

476

Page
engagement

1.6k

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

25%

New followers

Sentiment

Tweet activity

X

Impressions	3,766
Total engagements	122
Media engagements	38
Detail expands	26
Link clicks	18
Likes	16
Retweets	15
Profile clicks	9

Oct-Dec 2020

Tweet activity

X

Impressions	5,074
Total engagements	87
Detail expands	33
Media engagements	17
Retweets	11
Likes	10
Hashtag clicks	7
Link clicks	6
Profile clicks	3

Jan-Mar 2021

Tweet activity

X

Impressions	7,544
Total engagements	101
Link clicks	26
Detail expands	25
Likes	23
Retweets	13
Profile clicks	12
Hashtag clicks	2

Apr-Jun 2021

Tweet activity

X

Impressions	5,601
Media views	1,130
Total engagements	172
Detail expands	44
Media engagements	31
Profile clicks	27
Retweets	24
Likes	22
Link clicks	20
Hashtag clicks	3
Replies	1

Jul-Sep 2021

Top tweets

Engagement
Impressions

2,1%
VIRAL

155%

min. 56% (Jan-Mar 2021)
max 295,5% (Apr-Jun 2021)

Amplification Rate percentage

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IPERION HS

report

A dark grey network diagram consisting of four circular nodes connected by lines. The nodes are arranged in a zig-zag pattern: the first node is at the bottom left, the second is at the top middle, the third is at the bottom middle, and the fourth is at the top right. The word 'report' is positioned above the nodes, with the 'o' in 'report' corresponding to the top-middle node.

Created with mapchart.net

Follower Demographics

Data for: Location

Top locations

countries

Followers

564

Posts

58

Shares

77

Page views

884

Audience Grow Rate percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

84,4%

+476

Follower metrics ⓘ

Time range: Dec 31, 2020 - Sep 13, 2021 ▾

Aggregate organic and sponsored

Off

New followers

Heritage Science Online Forum

565 followers

2mo •

Silvia Prati from [Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna](#) is presenting a lecture on "Advanced diagnostic methods for the evaluation of cleaning treatments", a topic so relevant for all the participants at IPERION [#HSAcademy](#) Doctoral Summer School [#science](#) [#highereducation](#)

822
views

24 · 1 comment

Reactions

Like Comment Share Send

Top post

374

Engagement

18K

Impressions

0,4%
VIRAL

14%

Amplification Rate percentage

Comparing some data

Google

Italy - Spain - United States - United Kingdom - France -
Netherlands - Germany - China - Finland - Greece

Facebook

Italy - Spain - Greece - France - Portugal -
Poland - United Kingdom - Germany -
Netherlands - Malta - Mexico - Brazil - Egypt

LinkedIn

United Kingdom - Italy - Spain - Netherlands - United
States - Belgium - France

Location

Google

Male 54.2% Female 45.9%
Age 25-34

Facebook

Male 23.5% Female 76.5%
Age 25-34

User's identikit

Google

13k

Facebook

1.144

Twitter

782

Linkedin

564

Users: numbers

+**911** new followers
on social media
and **390** users registered
in the website
in the last year

#HeritageScience

Top countries

Top languages

Spelling variants used

Tweets Wall

Francesca Gherardi · Sep 17, 2021
@Fra_ghe...

How can hand-held XRF be used in the study of archaeological artefacts to answer research questions for archaeologists and conservators? Have a look at our new open-access technical brief:
pubs.rsc.org/en/content/art...

Francesca Gherardi
@Fra_gherardi

With examples from the 'London' and the 'Rooswijk' shipwrecks

@RoySocChem @HE_Archaeology
@rooswijk1740 #HeritageScience
#FClabs

11:40 AM · Sep 17, 2021

1 Copy link to Tw...

[Tweet your reply](#)

IPERION HS
@iperion_hs

Call for papers! The special issue on "Advanced Methods in #HeritageScience @Sus_MDPI is now open for submission. Special issue editors: Raffaella Fontana and Jana Striová, @CNR_INO. Deadline: 21 October 2021. Check out all the details here: bit.ly/3hzsAqr #openaccess

MACH
@MACHcamb

Do not miss today (12 BST) the #webinars organised by the #AI and the #Arts group at the Alan Turing Institute!

Topics: mathematical restoration of manuscripts and computerized paleographic investigation!

REGISTER HERE:
tinyurl.com/23k2a9pm

#HeritageScience #DataScience

Welcome! You are invited to join a ...
turing-uk.zoom.us

9:20 AM · Sep 17, 2021

4 Copy link to Tw...

[Tweet your reply](#)

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12:39 PM · Sep 16, 2021

13 Copy link to T...

[Tweet your reply](#)

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HeritageSci Forum UK
@HertSci_UK

We're doing a piece of work to map role descriptions to existing apprenticeship standards to see how existing standards can be used by the field of heritage science and where there are gaps.

Can you help us? bit.ly/2VsaPli #HeritageScience

4:43 PM · Sep 16, 2021

2 Copy link to Tw...

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@HertSci_UK

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4:43 PM · Sep 16, 2021

2 Copy link to T...

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FULL ANALYSIS

Related Hashtags

CORRELATION POPULARITY

#CulturalHeritage
#conservation
#SEAHAConf
#SCUD2016 #history #SEAHAConf2016 #olfactory
#IconTF16 #STEM

Mostly Tweeted By

ALL-TIME RECENT

Influence Specialization Followers

See Top Tweets

popularity trends

Google

89,9%

Facebook

16,6%

Twitter

25%

Linkedin

84,4%

Audience Grow Rate Percentage

It measures the speed at which your brand's following increases on social media.

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Facebook

44%

Twitter

155%

Linkedin

14%

Amplification Rate Percentage

IPERION HS Social Media & Web Report
(October 2020-September 2021)

Author: Laura Benassi

Year: September 2021

IPERION HS is a project funded by
the European Commission under

GA 871034